

Impact of climate change on coastal geomorphology and sea coast erosion -A case study of Swargadwar beach of Odisha.

Niranjan Sahoo*¹Dr. Uday Chatterjee*²

*¹ Department of Geography, Utkal University, Bhubaneswar, niranjansahoo743@gmail.com

*²Assistant Professor, Bhatler College, Dantan, raj.chatterjee459@gmail.com

Abstract

Due to rapid erosion near the inhabited areas of Bay of Bengal coast, human population residing there miserly suffer from urban flood and soil erosion other problems such as frequent intrusion salty water towards the residential area, landward extension of sea, extension of river mouth over large area, deposition of eroded materials in the sea under the impact of backwash and resultant landform from change of river course, rapid sea coast erosion and deposition has become a matter of grave concern for Geomorphologists. Under the influence of climate change, sea level is rising and hence Mangala river of Odisha is facing difficulties, causes river course changes in the taking place and modification of sea current across the coast is responsible for rapid erosion near Swargadwar beach of Odisha. This scientific paper is a study of coastal erosion near Swargadwar beach of Odisha and it dealt with the relation of course change of Mangala River under the impact of climate change.

Keywords: sea coast erosion; Mangala River; river course; resultant landforms; Swargadwar beach

Introduction:

Climate change has a huge impact on coastal geomorphology, as a result of which coastal geomorphology and its associated landforms are constantly shaping in the form of deposition near the shore, but when the erosion takes place due to several factors such as high tide surge, owing to unstable nature of sea under the impact of landward extension of sea and it became a matter of grave concern for the residential area because due to rapid erosion and tidal surge which easily enter and denude the coastal area at a rapid rate. The resulted landforms bear important for the Geomorphologists to squat out the consequence of raised problem. Moving water is the most important natural erosion agent. The coastal erosion is brought about mainly by the action of sea waves but also, in part, by the disintegration or degradation of sea cliffs by atmospheric agents such as rain, frost and tidal source. Sea wave erosion is accomplished primarily by the hydraulic pressure impact of waves striking the shore and by the abrasion by sand, pebbles agitated incessantly by the water wave-cut platform. Wave

impact and hydraulic action are usually most devastating to human-made coastal features such as breakwater moles. The impact and hydraulic action of storm waves are the most significant upon shores Swargadwar of Puri coastal district in Odisha has beard important for geomorphologists. Day by day Swargadwar coast of Puri facing toughest geological crises particularly in rainy season. According to the exports, the erosion near the Swargadwar of Puri coast has a close link to the course change of Mangala River which is merely 1000 meter away from the Swargadwar coast.

Literature review:

Mukherjee and Chatterjee (1997) mentioned that Beach and dune erosion is the major thrust of this region due to increased anthropogenic activity, recreational exploitation and unplanned urbanization. Also, the lack of CRZ implementation has given rise to land use problems in the sensitive area.

Coasts are dynamic systems undergoing adjustments of form and process (morphodynamics) at a different time and space scales in response to landform such as salt marshes (Adam, 2002)

Mani Murali et al (2009) studied the shoreline changes along the Paradip, Odisha, and east coast of India spatially and temporally using remote sensing methods from 1998 to 2005. Changes in the pattern of sediment movement, wave action, dredging, etc were found to increase the pressure on the coastal zone and lead to coastal geomorphologic changes.

Mukhopadhyay et al (2012) studied the shoreline change due to erosion/accretion for the 142 km Puri coast, Odisha. Multi-temporal Landsat satellite imageries from 1972-2010 were used to calculate the shoreline change rate using 'End Point Rate' (EPR) a statistical method, to predict the future shoreline change. It revealed that erosion was identified in the vicinity of Kushabadra estuary and Chandrabhaga beach, north of Puri.

Results from statistical analysis of a shoreline change spanning 38 years reveal that about 40% of shoreline along the Indian mainland is affected by erosion. Andhra Pradesh experiences coastal erosion at Uppada, Visakhapatnam and Bhimuniapatnam. Odisha coast experiences erosion at Gopalpur, Paradip, Penth and Sathbaya while WestBengal coast has experienced erosion at Digha, Bankiput and Gangasagar regions (Rajawat et al. 2014).

Objectives of the study:

- I. To analyze the effects of climate change (sea level rise, increased coastal erosion) on the study area.
- II. To find out the influence of climate change on Mangla river and its impact on Swargdwar beach erosion of Puri coast.

Result and discussion

Impact of climate change on coastal geomorphology:

We have noticed and experienced that there is sharp rise in global mean temperature. Due to the rise of temperature, the polar ice sheets melting, the density of seawater is increasing and volume of sea water is increasing adding more water in the sea. Rising sea-level results in a spatial shift of coastal geomorphology.

Many dynamic coastal landforms formed by the sea agents' act as an active agent on the coast. Manifest through the redistribution of coastal landforms comprising sub tidal bed forms, intertidal flats, salt marshes, shingle banks, sand dunes, cliffs and coastal lowlands (Pethick & Crooks 2000). Coastal areas are resulted by the active agent such as tide which plays an important role in the formation of different landforms.

Increases in mean global temperature would stimulate speculation that change in coastal landform would also put inhabitants of coastal area at risk and concerns to the impact on coastal geomorphology and the likely changing balance-accounts of the form and function of coastal habitats (IPCC 2001). The Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC AR4) predicts that the rise in global sea-level by 2100 will be in the range of 18–38 to 26–59 cm, depending on the emissions scenario (Meehl *et al.*, 2007)

Results of climate change and coastal erosion and recession:

Erosion and accretion are normal cyclical events on soft sediment coastlines. Where sea level is rising, a threshold is reached where erosion outstrips accretion and the beach will erode more than it is replenished. Once this tipping point is reached, the shoreline will tend to retreat. Sea-level rise is a key factor in causing coastal erosion and concerns about erosion risk have mounted in light of increased rates of sea-level rise predicted due to climate change (Masselink G and Russell P, 2013) While impacts of climate change at the coast are often primarily viewed in terms of adjustments to rate of accelerated sea-level rise (e.g. Aagaard and Sørensen, 2012; Anderson *et al.*, 2010; Ford, 2012; Jackson and McIlvenny, 2011; Kebede *et al.*, 2012; Strauss *et al.*, 2012). Coastal erosion is a common phenomenon than that of the recession on the Swargadwar coast of Puri coastal area. Although these erosion phenomena are seasonal in nature, particularly, it takes place in the rainy season but its, consequences last still the winter.

Erosion near Swargadwar coast of a Puri-Analarming issue for Geomorphologists:

Coastal erosion is the natural or anthropogenic process in which there occurs the loss of land or the removal of beach or dune sediments by wind, wave action, tidal currents, wave currents or drainage and various developmental activities along the coast. The change of coastal landform would change livelihood of the coastal inhabitant, the speculation that has been predicted about the rise of mean sea level of the global sea under the influence of climate change at a large scale (IPCC 2001). Over two million people (5% of the population) live and half of the highest-grade agricultural belt is found on coastal regions across the

globe. The coastal natural resources are suffering from a sustained net decline largely related to coastal squeeze of intertidal habitats (Carpenter & Pye 1996)

The study suggests that once upon a time Bay of Bengal was away from the present occupied position, but gradually it submerging land ward. Now it has ingresses towards landward by 200 feet. Due to tide surge with a heavy volume of water eroding the maximum land limits and hence coast erosion near Swargadwar coast of Puri is common for all coastal inhabitants.

Figure.1: Puri Swargadwar beach erosion in 2018

Source: Computed by authors

During 2006 the ingression of the sea was 50 feet towards landward, subsequently, it upgraded to more than 250 feet within 14 years (Figure.1 and Figure.2).

Figure.2: Shows the year wise erosion since 2006

Source: Computed by authors

Extensive field study suggests there are many causes behind the coastal erosion near the Puri Swargadwar coast, which are as follows:

Change of river course:

Here we are talking about changing course of Mangala River which is a tributary of the Bhargavi River falls in the sea near Sterling resort about 2 km west of Swargadwar. The bulk of sediment deposited in the river mouth and these sediments helps in the shifting of natural mouth across the coast. The real natural mouth of Mangal River has shifted over time and it has noticed that this shifting of river mouth has had a serious problem associated with the sea coast erosion near Swargadwar coast of Puri, and hence there is a need to analyse river course change (Figure.3) and its shifting of natural mouth as a regular phenomenon.

Figure: 3: Swargadwar beach erosion due to changes of river course of Mangla River

Source: Satellite Images 2017-2018

The shift of natural mouth:

The opening of Mangala mouth will facilitate the tidal ingress into the river so that it may annul the local energetic waves and current (Figure.4). The beach along Puri town is infringed by infrastructure and a slightest tidal inundation and temporary erosion creates panic to people(Beur 2016)

Figure: 4: Swargadwar beach erosion due to changes of river course of Mangla river

Source: Satellite Images 2017-2018

Figure: 5: Swargadwar beach erosion due to the shift of natural mouth of Mangla River

Source: Satellite Images 2017-2018

The cause of floods is largely attributed to the amount of fine-grained loess carried by the river from the Loess Plateau, which is continuously deposited along the bottom of its channel (Figure.5). The sedimentation causes natural dams to slowly fill up as river Mangala, a distributary of Mahanadi River which is a prime river of coastal deltaic regions flows in the coastal region of Odisha. The water volume of Mangala River is generally high in the monsoon season and the volume of its water is considered in other non-monsoonal seasons. As earlier we discussed that Mangala River is in the eastern coastal plain, this river carries a huge volume of sediments flows along with water. When the river reaches its old stage in the Puri district of Odisha the sediment deposition settles down on the coastal plain and this phenomenon is common in case of Mangala River.

High tide surge and coastal erosion near Puri Swargadwar coast:

Coastal landforms are the results of dynamic actions of wave and tide. (Pethick 1996, Pethick & Crooks 2000). For instance, whereas beach morphology responds to seasonal wave climate, any adjacent dune complex may respond over longer (decadal) timescales to larger storm events (Richie & Penland 1990, Orford et al. 1999). High tide generally takes the form of the huge volume of water, as sea water level increases due to polar ice melt, and water volume expanding and it became a positive factor for the formation of high tide. Location of Bay of Bengal in the tropical area also responsible for the formation of high tide. As this region comes under monsoonal climate, the coastal area receives more than 150 mm in a year and rain-fed rivers run and discharged their volume of water into the Bay of Bengal.

New tectonic plate moment:

According to some groups of geologists, the new tectonic movement caused by regular upwelling of magma beneath the earth crust under the sea water helps in the breaking of existed plate and formation of new plates. When Odisha Government reached out to geologist and IIT expert to find out the exact cause behind the massive soil erosion near Swargadwar coast of Puri, some geologist and IIT expert concluded that drifting of ocean plate towards the land helps in the formation of huge tide near the coast might be a cause of soil erosion near the Swargadwar coast of Puri. Because small oceanic plates those which are sliding towards the coast from the beneath of the ocean get stuck across the coasts and create immense pressure near the Swargadwar coast of Puri coastal profile and deposition on the upper part. Recent a model developed to find out the exact relationship between plate tectonic and coastal erosion model is applicable to estuaries, barriers and tidal flats to all the natural response of coastal systems to sea-level rise. This model examines the shifting rate of sea landward. (Masselink G and Russell P, 2013). Ocean current in the Bay of Bengal helps in the rapid ocean current toward landward as a result of which coastal erosion takes place at a rapid rate across sea coast in general and erosion near Swargadwar coast of Puri coastal area in particular.

Solution to take on massive soil erosion near the Swargadwar:

This section provides information on the implications of climate change and sea level rise for managing the natural and built environment in coastal areas. Management of the coast and planning new infrastructure or development must take climate change and sea level rise into account. To do this requires an understanding of localized coastal and marine processes and assessing risks to coastal values and infrastructure.

As pointed out by Nicholls *et al.* (2011), it is of particular importance to developing long-term strategic adaptation plans for the full range of possible climate change outcomes, both in terms of changes in sea level, extreme water level, storminess and wave climate.

The coastal management strategy (e.g., hard coastal defences, beach nourishment, and managed realignment) is also a key aspect for determining the long-term response of the coast to climate change effects, including sea-level rise. Managed realignment is likely to increase in the future as a key management strategy and although this will result in increased local erosion rates, the enhanced erosion may benefit other sections of the coast by reducing erosion or even causing accretion (Masselink G and Russell P, 2013).

Risk management and responding to hazardous events, such as storms, are critical to coastal planning and management in light of climate change. In some areas, planning for the retreat will also be required the coastal zone management not only restores marine resources but also such infract rural development it will also be helpful to pay attention for coastal geomorphology at the government level (HOC 1998, HOL 1999).

Digging of the natural old mouth of Mangala River:

As Mangala River flows through Mahanadi deltas of East coastal plain, it routinely forms mender at youthful stage till its mouth in general and helps in the shifting of the natural mouth of Mangala River particular. This Mangala River flow in the Mahanadi delta and hence this river flow along with maximum sediments.

On behalf of Odisha government, an extensive research has been carried out by geologist and IIT expert independently to find out the exact cause behind the massive soil erosion near Swargadwar coast. The experts say that shifting of river mouth might be a cause behind the formation of a huge tide near the coast of Puri. They suggested that there is a need of digging of the natural mouth of Mangala Rivers.

Geo-Synthetic tube:

The Integrated Coastal Zone Management Programme (ICZMP) has taken so many initiative to tackle the sea coast erosion across the Puri coast, Geo-synthetic tube is one of them which implemented the project with the help of IIT-Chennai, claimed they had gone for piloting geo-synthetic tube technology as hard engineering structure had many disadvantages including its high cost. Odisha has successfully deployed geo-synthetic tubes along its coast to tackle sea erosion. The tube has installed along the coast at Pentha in Brahmansahi Gram Panchayat in Kendrapara district. Although last year, geo-synthetic tube project had hit

controversy when one structure had ruptured. Subsequently, IIT-Chennai rectified the problem with its technical input but it is eco-friendly.

It also faced a number of challenges such as Mooted in 2008; the project had faced different hindrances, including the issue of forest clearance, coastal regulatory zone regulations and transportation of material to the coast during past 8 years. It needs to be mentioned that the Odisha coast is fairly stable as only 10 per cent of the coast is highly erosion prone. So it provides a very good opportunity for sustainable planning and management of the coast. Executive Engineer of the saline embankment division of the project, Purna Chandra Ratha said the project envisaged a 505-metre-long wall consisting of 241 geo-tubes.

Odisha is the second state in the country to have undertaken such a project on a pilot basis after neighbouring Andhra Pradesh, the official said. Past studies indicated that more than 36 per cent of the coast in Kendrapara faced the threat of erosion; the problem is most acute near habitations such as Pentha and Satbhaya in Kendrapara.

Geotextiles:

These are previous fabrics which are used in association with soil, have the ability to separate, filter, energize, protect, or drain. These are typically synthetic resin geotextile. As per the expectation of export this geotextile would be helpful in case of soil erosion near the Swargadwar coast of Puri.

Sand nourishment:

Beach nourishment is the supply of sand to the shore to increase the recreational value and/or to secure the beach against shore erosion by feeding sand on the beach. The coastal management strategy (e.g., hard coastal defences, beach nourishment, and managed realignment) is also likely to help other aspects of coastal zones, the enhanced erosion may benefit other sections of the coast by reducing erosion or even causing accretion. (Masselink G and Russell P, 2013).

Recommendation and Conclusions:

Coastal erosion due to heavy tidal surge under the impact of several factors such as high tide with huge volume of sea water in the rainy season, gravity motion, human interfaces on the coastal plain, modification coastal landform for human self-satisfaction are regarded as great cause behind the rapid coastal erosion in the climate change era, but have lots of knowledge to tackle these adverse situations by the implication of scientific equipment's. However current population explosion pushed human being to make a settlement along the sea coast also has had a great impact on coastal geomorphology, there are so many economic activities take place near the coast that tend to modify the natural landforms of sea coast and hence integrated coastal zone management act as positive factors in the direction of prevention of sea coast erosion. A minimum buffer zone should be left out for the abutting beach for the safe normal tidal activity of sea. Natural barriers such as mangroves and Casuarinas forests should be planted along the beach the buffer zone may be more effective than the implant of geosynthetic tubes, gabion boxes mattress against beach erosion. sand nourishment should be

along the beach. No structure should be constructed along the erosion-prone beach, as will affect the scenic beauty of the Puri coast. Redigging of the River Mangala's natural mouth should take place on a regular basis, as the shifting of the natural mouth of the River Mangala is treated as problems behind erosion near Swargadwar.

References:

1. Aagaard T and Sørensen P (2012) Coastal profile response to sea-level rise: A process-based approach. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms* 37: 354–362.
2. Anderson JB, Milliken KT, Wallace D, et al. (2010) Coastal impact underestimated from rapid sea level rise. *EOS, Transactions American Geophysical Union* 91 (23): 205–212.
3. Beura D (2016) Coastal Erosion in Odisha: Causes and Consequences with Special Reference to Puri Beach Erosion, Research Gate.
4. Carpenter, K. & Pye, K. 1996. Salt marsh Changes in England and Wales – its History and Causes. Environment Agency R&D Technical Report W12. Marlow: HR Wallingford Ltd & Foundation for Water Resources.
5. Ford M (2012) Shoreline changes on an urban atoll in the central Pacific Ocean: Majuro Atoll, Marshall Islands. *Journal of Coastal Research* 28: 11–22.
6. HOC (House of Commons). 1998. Flood and Coastal Defence. Agricultural Committee Second Report. London: HMSO. HOL (House of Lords).1999. Biodiversity in the European Union.
7. IPCC.2001.*Third Assessment Report – Climate Change 2001*, vols 1–3. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
8. Jackson AC and McIlvenny J (2011) Coastal squeeze on rocky shores in northern Scotland and some possible ecological impacts. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology* 400: 314–321.
9. Kebede A, Nicholls RJ, Hanson S, et al. (2012) Impacts of climate change and sea-level rise: A preliminary case study of Mobassa, Kenya. *Journal of Coastal Research* 28: 8–19.
10. Masselink, G. and Russell, P. (2013) Impacts of climate change on coastal erosion, *MCCIP Science Review 2013*, 71-86, doi:10.14465/2013.arc09.071-086
11. Meehl, G.A. (2007) *Global climate projections. In: Climate Change 2007: The Physical Science Basis. The contribution of Working Group I to the Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*, pp. 433-497, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK.
12. Nicholls, R.J.*et al.* (2011) Sea-level rise and its possible impacts are given a ‘beyond 4oC world’ in the twenty-first century. *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. A*, 369, 161-181.
13. Orford, J.D., Cooper, J.A.G. & McKenna, J. 1999. Meso scale temporal changes to fore dunes at Inch Spit, south-west Ireland. *Z. Geomorphol.* 43: 439–461.

14. Pethick, J.S. 1996. The geomorphology of mudflat. In Nordstrom, K.F. & Roman, C.T. (eds) *Estuarine Shores: Evolution, Environment and Human Health*: 41–62. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
15. Pethick, J.S. & Crooks, S. 2000. Development of a coastal vulnerability index: a geomorphological perspective. *Environ. Conserv.* 27: 359–367.
16. Richie, W. & Penland, S. 1990. Aeolian sand bodies of the south Louisiana coast. In Nordstrom, K.F., Pusty, N.P. & Carter, R.W.G. (eds) *Coastal Dunes*: 105–127. Chichester: John Wiley
17. Strauss BH, Ziemiński R, Weiss JL, et al. (2012) tidally adjusted estimates of topographic vulnerability to sea level rise and flooding for the contiguous United States. *Environmental Research Letters* 7: 014033.
18. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change Fourth Assessment Report (IPCC 2007).